

Creation of a coating composition based on protein hydrolysate for chrome leather coating and improvement of its technology.

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Annotation: *The article presents the development of a wear complex for leather, prepared using acrylic primer compositions containing alkylcarbonyl ethanlates for chrome leather coating. The study investigates the ability of the AK-224 emulsion preparation to provide the main quality indicator of film-forming agents when used for chrome leather coating.*

Key words: *Chrome, coating dyeing, chemical reagents, leather.*

The processing of chrome leather materials with coating dyes and the improvement of its technology, especially the creation of coating compositions based on protein hydrolysates, is one of the urgent issues in modern leather industry. The main goal of this direction is to further strengthen the leather, enhance its quality, while simultaneously producing environmentally friendly products without harming the environment. Chrome leather is a high-quality material, primarily made from animal hides (often from cattle and sheep). This material is treated with chrome salts, resulting in leather that is strong, elastic, and durable. However, chrome-treated leather has a negative environmental impact, as chrome salts can be highly toxic.

Typically, the primary finishing of leather consists of an aqueous composition, where casein or synthetic polymers such as melamine or urea formaldehyde condensation products are used and then dried. It is proposed to add polyisocyanate to the aqueous composition and further treat it with heat. The composition may contain aqueous casein or synthetic polymers. Diisocyanates are dispersed in an aqueous state, meaning that the reaction product of ethylene oxide and polyisocyanate can be introduced. However, it has been shown that this does not provide a high-quality coating for leather. During the exploitation process, the physical-mechanical properties of the leather deteriorate, increasing the stiffness and opacity of the coating. A wear complex for leather, prepared using acrylic primer compositions containing alkylcarbonyl ethanlates for chrome leather coating, has been applied.

The results of the research [2] show that the use of natural naphthenic alkylcarboxyethanlates allows the production of high-quality and stable coatings. In chrome leather coating, the emulsion AK-224 preparation has been studied to provide the main quality indicator of film-forming agents. In this technology, it is considered that no color change should occur when finishing white and light-colored suede leathers. Furthermore, it was found that the resulting coating films were not sufficiently resistant to cold.

Additionally, in [1], collagen hydrolysate was extracted from chrome-tanned leathers treated with various tannins. They possess the property of forming polymeric films during the finishing processes. In the process of finishing chrome-tanned natural leathers with tanning agents [4], the leathers are dried, stretched, softened in a drum, pulled on frames for drying, subjected to final finishing, and additionally pressed on frames. A pigment-free primer layer is applied, and the leathers are first pressed. For final finishing, a water solution of shellac is applied twice, and then they are pressed again. After the final finishing, the leathers are further pressed and softened by working them in a drum. Then, they are stretched on special frames for additional drying. However, these technologies are intended for leather surface coating and decorative finishing. In the process of pressing at high temperatures, the coating layers become tacky and sticky. Thus, this composition does not have the most important characteristics for decorative embossed leather, as the hot metal matrix adheres to the working surface.

The wear process of chrome-tanned leather coatings, i.e., the self-degradation of polymers during the storage and use of leather products, affects their properties. Wear is the result of the influence of various chemical reagents, temperature, light, radioactive radiation, and mechanical deformation on the leather and its coating, leading to destruction or structural changes [3].

Renewal of Protein Hydrolysates: The technology of protein hydrolysis can be further improved. By using proteins derived from new biological sources, more environmentally friendly and efficient coatings can be created.

Application of Nanotechnology: The composition of coatings can be improved using nanomaterials and nanoparticles. Nano-molecules adhere strongly to the surface of leather, ensuring high-quality coatings.

New Dye Systems: Creating new environmentally friendly dyes for chrome leather and combining them with protein hydrolysates can be one of the most important steps in modern technology.

This article analyzes the stages of the finishing process to eliminate the shortcomings in chrome-tanned leather and presents the method. The use of emulsions of various acrylic polymers in the finishing process is recommended. The evaluation of the physical and chemical properties of acrylic emulsions showed that the adhesion of leathers with higher moisture content is stable. When compared to leathers obtained through traditional processing technologies, chrome-tanned leathers show higher tensile strength limits and improved air permeability. Creating a coating composition based on protein hydrolysates for chrome leather materials helps improve their ecological cleanliness, durability, and functionality. The improvement of this technology will not only promote the development of the industry but also reduce its environmental impact. In the future, the development of this field may lead to the production of more efficient and innovative coating materials.

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